

Bound Electrons and Radiation Due To Acceleration

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Classical electrodynamics shows that a radiating charge accelerates. The calculation is based on the assumption that the center-of-mass of the charge accelerates with a given dv/dt , but that a signal is sent out a time x, t' and when it reaches the measurement point, the particle is at a different x, t . The signal is taken to travel at the speed of light in a vacuum, c , and it is assumed that Maxwell's equations are preserved in such a calculation. The idea is that one calculates the electric and vector potentials using a retarded time for the position r given a t and obtains the electric and magnetic fields using the usual equations. One then finds that $1/u_0 E \times B$ has a term which does not drop off faster than $1/r^2$ meaning that a nonzero flux over a surface area (as the surface area tends to infinite) implies a loss of momentum flux (i.e. photons are radiated).

We suggest that the above calculation assumes one can follow the particle in a Newtonian manner in space and time, i.e. resolve time at each tiny instant. In the quantum case, one, however, has: $\Delta t = \hbar / E$. If one assumes that a signal travels about 10^{-10} m in an atom, then the associated time is 3.3×10^{-19} s. We find, however, that Δt values range from the order of 10^{-17} s (ground state hydrogen) to about 10^{-19} for a speed of 5×10^7 m/s. Thus, one has a quantum uncertainty of time during this signal interval and cannot assume that the particle is accelerating uniformly or that one can make calculations assuming that one knows what is happening in shorter times. We suggest then that one cannot really use the classical electrodynamic approach of calculating radiation given off by an accelerating charge in a quantum case for which Δt is generally higher than the time taken for the signal to travel a maximum distance. We argue that one does not have sufficient time resolution to justify such a calculation.

Quantum Calculation of a Bound Charged Particle

The nonrelativistic Schrodinger equation, which may be applied to an electron bound by a charged nucleus (e.g. hydrogen etc) does not consider the charge as accelerating. (Neither does the more accurate Dirac equation treatment of the same atom.) In particular, both the quantum nonrelativistic and relativistic treatments of a bound charged particles are based on a superposition of constant momentum/speed states, i.e.

$$W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad \text{where } p = \text{momentum} = \text{number} \quad ((1))$$

We have argued in a previous note that the electron is essentially in one constant velocity state or another and a constant speed state does not accelerate, even in classical electrodynamics. A change from one p value to another, however, would entail acceleration in the Newtonian picture. This framework, however, assumes that one may follow the particle at all x and t and involves the notion of retarded time. We briefly outline the calculation.

Radiation from an Accelerating Charge According to Classical Electrodynamics

We consider a point charge and use the approach of (1) (which is consistent with special relativity). (1) writes the electrostatic and vector magnetic potentials as:

$$\Phi_{\text{electric}} = \frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{1}{1 + v \cdot n/c} \right) \quad ((1a))$$

$$\mathbf{A}_{\text{vector magnetic}} = \frac{1}{4\pi \epsilon_0} \left\{ \frac{v/c}{[R (1 + v \cdot n/c)]} \right\} \quad ((1b))$$

Here, the particle is at x_1 moving along the x axis with speed v . A measuring point exists at P . The vector R_1 joins the x_1 point of the center-of-mass of the point particle to P . Due to a signal moving at speed c , the signal was sent before the particle reached x_1 , namely at x from which a vector R reaches P . n is a unit vector along R . In particular, (1) uses r_2 vector and t_2 to represent the x point and P , t to represent the measurement point and time. Then:

$$(P_x - x_2)^2 + (P_y - y_2)^2 + (P_z - z_2)^2 = c^2 (t - t_2)^2 \quad ((2))$$

To make a long story short: E (Electric field) = $-\frac{dA}{dt} \text{partial} - \text{grad } \phi$ ((3a)) and

$$\mathbf{B} \text{ (magnetic field vector)} = \text{grad} \times \mathbf{A} \quad ((3b))$$

When performing the derivatives, one finds that because $v(t)$ (i.e. accelerates) one may act on it instead of an R vector with a derivative and so the fields do not drop in R as fast as they would for a charged particle moving at a constant v . Thus,

Momentum flux = $1/\mu_0 \mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ has a term which does not drop faster than $R \cdot R$ which is the radius of a sphere from the x point. Taking the limit of $R \rightarrow \infty$ means that one has momentum moving out of the sphere and this is said to be radiation (i.e. photons) leaving the accelerating charge.

The main point we wish to make is that for this calculation to hold, one must have Newtonian time resolution, i.e. very sharp time resolution. Otherwise, one cannot take derivatives in the first place as they involve $dx \rightarrow 0$, $dt \rightarrow 0$. The problem is that in quantum mechanics dx and dt do not tend to zero. For a free particle they are dictated by:

$$\Delta x = \hbar/p \quad ((4a)) \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta t = \hbar/E \quad ((4b))$$

If these values are very small compared with times required for the signal to reach the measurement point, then one may dismiss Δx and Δt as equivalent to small errors of measurement. If this is not the case, however, then there is bad resolution and one cannot take any derivatives involving dx and dt less than ((4a,b)). We thus calculate ((4a)) and ((4b)) and compare to a signal time.

Numbers for an Electron in an Atom

We consider some simple estimates. First we assume that a signal in an atom travels about 10^{-10} m. Then:

$$d=ct \rightarrow 10^{-10} = 3 \times 10^8 t \text{ or } \text{time for a signal} = 3.3 \times 10^{-19} \text{ s} \quad ((5))$$

In the ground state of a hydrogen atom, an electron is said to have a rough speed of 2.2×10^6 m/s (2). Then:

$$\Delta t = 6.6 \times 10^{-34} / \{(3.14 \times 9 \times 10^{-31}) (2.2)(2.2) 10^{12}\} = 4.8 \times 10^{-17} \text{ s} \quad ((6))$$

Thus, 10^{-17} s is the resolution which is much worse than 10^{-19} sec and so we argue that one cannot perform the classical electrodynamic calculation which suggests that radiation is given off an accelerating charge. (Note: Time derivatives would involve dt values much smaller than 10^{-19} s.)

If one considers $v = 10^7$ m/s, then one obtains a Δt of about 2.3×10^{-18} s.

For $v = 5 \times 10^7$ m/s, one obtains $\Delta t \approx 1 \times 10^{-19}$ s.

In all of these cases there is no justification for taking time derivatives within the 3.3×10^{-19} s signal travel time and the classical calculation demonstrating radiation of photons cannot be performed, we argue. That, of course, does not prove that an accelerating charge in an atom cannot radiate, simply that the standard classical calculation demonstrating radiation does not hold. Experimentally, however, there does not seem to be radiation. Theoretically there may be no radiation (or else there are theories which have an electron radiated and then reabsorb the radiation). The point we make is that one should not necessarily expect radiation based on the classical electrodynamic equations when one does not have time resolutions to perform the partial time derivatives.

Experimental Evidence for a Lack of Time and Spatial Resolutions in Quantum Mechanics

Both a massive particle and a photon interfere with a 2-slit apparatus, which suggests that there is a uncertainty in interaction in x of the order of the slit separation. Formally, it is suggested that ((4a)) and ((4b)) hold or that a photon or massive particle is described probabilistically by:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((7))$$

This approach describes quantitatively the 2-slit experiment. As a result, there is experimental evidence for a lack of resolution in quantum mechanics/photon physics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that if one uses the quantum results for a constant speed, then $\Delta x = \hbar/p$ and $\Delta t = \hbar/E$. The time resolution is not sufficient for one to take the partial derivatives which are used in the classical electrodynamical calculator which shows that an accelerating point charge radiates photons. If one uses $x=ct$ with $x=10^{-10}$ m, one obtains $t= 3.3 \times 10^{-19}$ s and dt derivatives intervals would be much smaller, while the quantum dt is of the order 10^{-17} sec to 10^{-19} sec. Thus, we argue that one cannot use classical electrodynamical calculations which demonstrate that an accelerating charge radiates. This does not prove that an electron bound in an atom cannot radiate photons, but experimentally one does not see it, and one cannot expect it based on a classical equation which requires time resolution which is not present quantum mechanically, we argue.

References

1. Reitz, J and Milford, F. and Christy, R. Foundations of Electromagnetic Theory Addison Wesley 1980 P 479-481
2. <https://chemistry.stackexchange.com/questions/26501/how-fast-do-electrons-move-around-the-nucleus>